

POSSIBILITIES OF USING INNOVATIVE METHODS IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE LESSONS TO DEVELOP THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS IN NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: The article discusses the issue of increasing the effectiveness of teaching the Russian language in non-philological universities. It also describes innovative methods and approaches to teaching in Russian during training. Opportunities to empower teachers with respect to modern teaching methods are identified to identify the key components necessary to implement this model of teaching students Russian as a foreign language in a university setting.

Keywords: communication, innovative learning, process, skills formation, motivation, educational technologies, motivation.

1 INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly developing digital economy, one of the problems in preparing highly educated specialists in the higher education system is having a different level of knowledge of a foreign language, for example, Russian. This situation is explained by the fact that the formation of Russian language skills is individual in nature, it depends on the characteristics of the psychophysiological nature of the student, including memory, attention, individual pace of learning, as well as the level of speech culture, vocabulary, general communication skills, level of interest and motivation for learning the Russian language [3]. As a result, in Russian language lessons, a university teacher is faced with the presence in a group of strong students, intermediate level students, as well as weak students who know only simple Russian.

In this regard, the teaching staff is often faced with the difficult problem of effectively organizing the educational process in the classroom: if the teacher works with an emphasis on the weak, this can lead to the fact that average and strong students will not accept new knowledge. As a result, there is no progress in learning, which leads to a decrease in their motivation to learn the Russian language [1]. If the teacher focuses on strong students, weak and average students will not be able to comprehend the material that is difficult for them, they will also not move forward and, accordingly, their motivation to read will decrease. This situation, in turn, leads to a decrease in efficiency, that is, the quality of training, which in our work is defined as the level of development of Russian language proficiency by type of speech activity.

2 Materials and methods

Today, educational technologies are a means of achieving subject and meta-subject results, as well as individual student results [1]. The teacher's system of work to ensure the results of teaching the Russian language should include the implementation of the following technologies:

At the same time, A.V. Volovin states that "... a language cannot be taught at all, a language can only be learned" [4].

Obviously, the main role in this approach is played by the student's personality, his motivation, abilities and goals. The massive development of the Internet has expanded the range of information resources. Most information resources are currently available on the Internet in Russian, and without their knowledge, network users limit themselves and cannot access large amounts of data [3].

New information technologies used in education are developed in such a way that with their help it is possible to carry out ordinary types of educational work: lectures and practical exercises, consultations, tests; only at a high technical level [4]. Faced with such realities, students of non-linguistic universities understand that the foreign language they are studying, especially Russian, is not only a means of communication, but also a means of knowledge, self-development, broadening their horizons and interests, and satisfying personal needs. In our opinion, the most difficult thing in teaching the Russian language at non-specialized faculties of universities is the principle of complexity, the principle of verbal basis and speech development, the personal orientation of learning and the activity-based nature, especially when considering texts using terms in the specialty.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The problem is that it is not always possible to divide non-major students into small groups. It consists of skill development through innovative education and self-education. Fundamentalism, together with its emphasis on honesty and the pursuit of individual interests, creates the key features of the new educational paradigm. Fundamental scientific and humanitarian education should provide a holistic understanding of the modern natural and scientific landscape of the world, create a scientific basis for assessing the results of professional activity, promote creative development and the correct choice of an individual life program.

It should be noted that for a long time now, learning the Russian language has not been reduced to passive memorization of new words and phrases. Uniformity, tedious checking of grammatical rules and the ability to translate a Russian phrase into Uzbek at best - these are the limits of mastery in mastering foreign means of communication.

Although many approaches to studying the Russian language and methods have long been known in the world, a real revolution in the methodology of teaching the Russian language in our country occurred only at the end of the XX - beginning of the XXI century [5]. Approaches and goals have changed. Today everyone is learning Russian. The number of techniques has also increased in proportion to the number of people.

However, each of the techniques has its pros and cons. The principles of the old school are subject to sharp criticism, although their current application has borne fruit. The question arises: at what cost could these results be achieved? Typically, to master a language, one had to spend a lot of time translating, reading texts, memorizing new words, doing various exercises and reviewing books, devoting time to retelling. To change

the type of activity, it was proposed to write an essay or dictation.

One of the oldest techniques is classical or fundamental. The goal of the classical method is not only to study, but also to understand the subtleties and details of the principles of the Russian language. The main task of classical methodology is the formation of the grammatical base of the translated language [6]. This technique is well known to those who are just starting to learn Russian at school. It is noteworthy that it is chosen by many language universities, both in Uzbekistan and in other countries of Central Asia.

One such method is called the linguistic sociocultural method. Proponents of the above style argued that modern Russian should not be a set of grammatical rules. Conversely, the absence of non-linguistic factors makes learning Russian boring and pointless. Supporters of the linguo-sociocultural style raise the Russian language to the level of a communicative medium, which not only helps a person speak, but also gives him the opportunity to express himself. Following the principles of the linguo-sociocultural method, we can confidently say that the Russian language is a unique mirror reflecting the way of life, customs, culture and history of the language.

However, one of the most popular methods of teaching foreign languages recently is the communicative method, which ranks first in statistical rankings and calculations. This method has proven itself well in Russia[7]. Continuing to conquer the world, a communicative technique has come to us, used in the leading language universities of our republic. The methodology is based on a combination of two main methods of teaching the Russian language: traditional and modern.

As the name suggests, communication plays an important role in communication. The main goal of this technique is to overcome the language barrier [3]. Most importantly, it frees a person from the fear of a foreign language, from the fear of speaking Russian, and at the same time develops other language skills, in particular speaking and writing, reading, listening, and so on.

It should be noted that grammar is studied in the process of speaking and communicating in Russian by students of non-linguistic universities. According to this principle, students first memorize and memorize language formulas and phrases and only then analyze

the grammatical errors found in the memorized phrases. The name itself speaks of the special place of communicative practice in communicative methodology.

Didactic materials are collections of tasks, dictations, exercises, as well as examples of abstracts and essays, presented in electronic form, usually in the form of a simple set of text files in the following formats: doc, .rtf and .txt. The inconvenience of this almost traditional knowledge control is that you still have to independently check students' handwritten work and assign a score and grade for it.

In addition, students at non-linguistic universities need to develop skills in studying dictionaries. The systematic accumulation and expansion of vocabulary is one of the most important tasks when teaching the Russian language. It is difficult to communicate without knowledge of grammar, but without knowledge of words it is impossible to communicate; you can neither express nor understand the most basic phrases. Successful communication with people around you and solving specific problems depends on the volume of your vocabulary [6].

Communication techniques are aimed at developing skills and competencies in speaking Russian. It should be noted that the application of the methodology directly affects the structure of the lesson. In Russian language lessons, it is often necessary to develop tasks for the ability to use game situations, conduct group work, find errors and compare. As a rule, such activities not only make memory actively function, but also logical thinking, which allows you to develop analytical and imaginative thinking skills and encourages the expression of ideas.

Games are also a challenging task for teachers in the process of teaching and learning the Russian language in non-linguistic universities. Play games through the audience, individual, pair and group work possible. Grouping, pairing and the four types of group work are very important if each student has oral practice in using the language.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Today, the development of modern information and communication technologies creates the latest interactive resources for learning the Russian language, including the latest generation computers, the Internet, television programs, newspapers and magazines. It is very important to put all of the above into practice. This helps to awaken students' interest in the country's history, culture, customs of the target language and helps to develop the skills they will need in the future. Education is an active interaction between teacher and students, and it cannot be one-sided. It depends on how

successful the learning process is for the teacher. It is clear that each teacher is guided by his personal experience in choosing working methods. However, based on the results of experimental and practical work, it can be noted that the use of various techniques within the framework of communicative, inductive, and deductive methods gives a positive result and undoubtedly helps to increase the effectiveness of learning. The author also tries to adhere to a teaching method called "mixed". This will allow you to achieve your goals and help you achieve better results.

Thus, the practice of teaching the Russian language to students of non-linguistic universities on the basis of innovative teaching methods contributes to the development of a motivation mechanism in students, which is very important and must be taken into account when teaching the language in a foreign language audience. Educational activities make it possible to simulate more adequate situations and conditions of foreign language communication compared to traditional teaching, thereby promoting the development of students' communicative knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for real communication in a multilingual space..

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